

Supplemental Table S1. Oligonucleotide sequences

The reverse oligonucleotides used for the cloning of the AtUMAMIT CDS contain a Y (= C or T) at the position of the stop codon, so that fragments that have a TGG (encodes a Trp in the sense orientation) can be cleaved by *KpnI* at that site, while the fragment that have a TAG (stop codon in the sense orientation) cannot. This enables the generation of clones with or without stop with one single oligonucleotide, one BP reaction, and screenable by restriction analysis with *KpnI*.

Name	Sequence (5'-3')	Goal
AtUMAMIT01 attB1	GACAAGTTTGTACAAAAAGCAGGCTCAAGAAGAAAATGGCAGCTCC	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT01 Kpn attB2	GACCACTTTGTACAAGAAAGCTGGGTACYATTTACCACTCTCATCTCTGTAATGAA	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT02 attB1	GACAAGTTTGTACAAAAAGCAGGCTCAATCGGAAAGATGACGGCG	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT02 Kpn attB2	GACCACTTTGTACAAGAAAGCTGGGTACYAGTCTGCAGATTTACAGAGGAACT	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT02p attB1	GACAAGTTTGTACAAAAAGCAGGCTCGGTTTGGTTTCAGTTTGA	Promoter cloning
AtUMAMIT02p attB2	GACCACTTTGTACAAGAAAGCTGGGTAGCCGTCATCTTCCGATTT	Promoter cloning
AtUMAMIT03 attB1	GACAAGTTTGTACAAAAAGCAGGCTCAATGGAGAGTACGGTGGAAAGAGAG	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT03 Kpn attB2	GACCACTTTGTACAAGAAAGCTGGGTACYAATCATCGGATTTTGGTGAAGAGAT	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT03p attB1	GACAAGTTTGTACAAAAAGCAGGCTCGACGCAGTTACGGCAA	Promoter cloning
AtUMAMIT03p attB2	GACCACTTTGTACAAGAAAGCTGGGTATCTTCCACCGTACTCTCCAT	Promoter cloning
AtUMAMIT04 attB1	GACAAGTTTGTACAAAAAGCAGGCTCAAAGAGAAAATGGGGAAAGGAGTA	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT04 Kpn attB2	GACCACTTTGTACAAGAAAGCTGGGTACYACACTTCAGATTCAGAATTAATCTTCTTG	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT04p attB1	GACAAGTTTGTACAAAAAGCAGGCTTTTGGGGTTTCTTGGTATCT	Promoter cloning
AtUMAMIT04p attB2	GACCACTTTGTACAAGAAAGCTGGGTATGATACTACTCTTCCCAT	Promoter cloning
AtUMAMIT05 attB1	GACAAGTTTGTACAAAAAGCAGGCTCAATGGCGGATAACACCGATAAT	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT05 Kpn attB2	GACCACTTTGTACAAGAAAGCTGGGTACYAAACATTGTCCGTTGACTGATGG	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT06 attB1	GACAAGTTTGTACAAAAAGCAGGCTCAAGAACGATGTCTCCGATACCG	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT06 Kpn attB2	GACCACTTTGTACAAGAAAGCTGGGTACYAGGAAGAAATTAATGGTTGACTAATAGG	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT07 attB1	GACAAGTTTGTACAAAAAGCAGGCTCAGCCATGCAATTTTTTTGTGTAAT	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT07 Kpn attB2	GACCACTTTGTACAAGAAAGCTGGGTACYAAGACAAAAGAGGCTTCTTAGAGTCG	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT08 attB1	GACAAGTTTGTACAAAAAGCAGGCTCATTTTGTGTTGAAAAATGATGAAGA	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT08 Kpn attB2	GACCACTTTGTACAAGAAAGCTGGGTACYAAAGCAAGAGAGGCTTCTGAAGAT	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT09 attB1	GACAAGTTTGTACAAAAAGCAGGCTCAATGTCGATGGAGGAGATTAGTAGC	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT09 Kpn attB2	GACCACTTTGTACAAGAAAGCTGGGTACYATGGCTCTGGATAGTCTTTTTCA	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT10 attB1	GACAAGTTTGTACAAAAAGCAGGCTCATTTGATATGGGGTTAAAGATGTCA	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT10 Kpn attB2	GACCACTTTGTACAAGAAAGCTGGGTACYACGAGAAACCCACCGCCACTTTA	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT11 attB1	GACAAGTTTGTACAAAAAGCAGGCTCAAAGATGGGATTAAGGATGTCAGAA	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT11 Kpn attB2	GACCACTTTGTACAAGAAAGCTGGGTACYAGTTAGGTCGTGAAACGCTATGC	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT11p attB1	GACAAGTTTGTACAAAAAGCAGGCTCGGATAAGCAATTCTAGGCAGA	Promoter cloning
AtUMAMIT11p attB2	GACCACTTTGTACAAGAAAGCTGGGTATTCTGACATCCTTAATCCCATC	Promoter cloning
AtUMAMIT12 attB1	GACAAGTTTGTACAAAAAGCAGGCTCTTCAGTGATGGAGGAAGTAAAGA	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT12 Kpn attB2	GACCACTTTGTACAAGAAAGCTGGGTACYAACCGTTAAGTGAGACTGTTTCTACA	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT12p attB1	GACAAGTTTGTACAAAAAGCAGGCTCCTTCCAAGTGCAGAATAATGA	Promoter cloning
AtUMAMIT12p attB2	GACCACTTTGTACAAGAAAGCTGGGTACTCTTCTTACTTCTCCATCA	Promoter cloning
AtUMAMIT13 attB1	GACAAGTTTGTACAAAAAGCAGGCTCAGATCTTGACAGATGGCATGTAT	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT13 Kpn attB2	GACCACTTTGTACAAGAAAGCTGGGTACYAGACTGATTCTATCACTGTTCTTCTTG	CDS cloning

AtUMAMIT14 attB1	GACAAGTTTGTACAAAAAGCAGGCTCAGATATGGCTTTAAAAACATGGAAG	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT14 Kpn attB2	GACCACTTTGTACAAGAAAGCTGGGTACYAGACTGATTCATTGGTGTTAGGCCT	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT14 E122R	TGGCATGGATCTTTAGACTTCGTAAGGTTAACGTCAAGAAAAT	Mutagenesis
AtUMAMIT14 G144V	GAACAATTGTGACAGTTGGTGTGCAATGCTTATGACTGTTGT	Mutagenesis
AtUMAMIT14 G315V	GAGCAATAGTGATAGTTCTTGTCTCTATTCGGTTTTGTGGG	Mutagenesis
AtUMAMIT14 G33V	CGAAATTCGCACTGAACCAAGTTATGAGTCTCACGTTCTAGC	Mutagenesis
AtUMAMIT14 K134E	AGAAAATACACAGCCAAGCCGAAATTTAGGAACAATTGTGAC	Mutagenesis
AtUMAMIT15 attB1	GACAAGTTTGTACAAAAAGCAGGCTCAAGAATGAAGTTTGAGAGAGCAAGG	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT15 Kpn attB2	GACCACTTTGTACAAGAAAGCTGGGTACYACTCTTGAGACCGAGCTGCTG	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT17 attB1	GACAAGTTTGTACAAAAAGCAGGCTCAAGGAAGAAAATGAAAGGAGGAAAG	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT17 Kpn attB2	GACCACTTTGTACAAGAAAGCTGGGTACYACACTTGGGTATTGTTAGTCACACC	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT18 attB1	GACAAGTTTGTACAAAAAGCAGGCTCAATAAAGATGAAAGGTGGAAGCATG	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT18 Kpn attB2	GACCACTTTGTACAAGAAAGCTGGGTACYAGTACTGGTAACCACACCGTTAGT	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT19 attB1	GACAAGTTTGTACAAAAAGCAGGCTCAATGGGGAGAGGGTTAATGAATAGT	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT19 Kpn attB2	GACCACTTTGTACAAGAAAGCTGGGTACYAAATCTCAACTTGAGTAGTAGTAGCC	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT20 attB1	GACAAGTTTGTACAAAAAGCAGGCTCATCAATAACCATGGAGGGTGTAGT	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT20 Kpn attB2	GACCACTTTGTACAAGAAAGCTGGGTACYATATTCAGATGTGTTACTATGCGC	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT21 attB1	GACAAGTTTGTACAAAAAGCAGGCTCAATGGACATGGAGTCGAAGAAAC	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT21 Kpn attB2	GACCACTTTGTACAAGAAAGCTGGGTACYAACTAATGACAACCTTCACTTCATTG	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT22 attB1	GACAAGTTTGTACAAAAAGCAGGCTCATATTACACGATGATGATGGAGCAC	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT22 Kpn attB2	GACCACTTTGTACAAGAAAGCTGGGTACYAGACGATGATAAATCTTCTATAATTTCTTT	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT22p attB1	GACAAGTTTGTACAAAAAGCAGGCTCTTTAGGAGCATCTCCAAGTGT	Promoter cloning
AtUMAMIT22p attB2	GACCACTTTGTACAAGAAAGCTGGGTAGGCTTTGTGCTCCATCATC	Promoter cloning
AtUMAMIT23 attB1	GACAAGTTTGTACAAAAAGCAGGCTCAGAAATGAAAGATATAACGGCAATG	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT23 Kpn attB2	GACCACTTTGTACAAGAAAGCTGGGTACYAAGGGACATTTGACTTAATGTTGG	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT23p attB1	GACAAGTTTGTACAAAAAGCAGGCTAAATTGTTGGCAGGAACTAGAT	Promoter cloning
AtUMAMIT23p attB2	GACCACTTTGTACAAGAAAGCTGGGTACATTGCCGTTATATCTTTTCAT	Promoter cloning
AtUMAMIT24 attB1	GACAAGTTTGTACAAAAAGCAGGCTCAGGAGAAATGAAGAGTGATGTTGCA	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT24 Kpn attB2	GACCACTTTGTACAAGAAAGCTGGGTACYAGGGGACATCTCTATTTACTGATGAA	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT24p attB1	GACAAGTTTGTACAAAAAGCAGGCTCGTATAGGGAACAATAGGAACA	Promoter cloning
AtUMAMIT24p attB2	GACCACTTTGTACAAGAAAGCTGGGTACTTCATTTCTCCACATT	Promoter cloning
AtUMAMIT25 attB1	GACAAGTTTGTACAAAAAGCAGGCTCAGAGATGGCTAAATCAGATATGTTGC	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT25 Kpn attB2	GACCACTTTGTACAAGAAAGCTGGGTACYAAGGCGATGTAGACCTTGTTGG	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT26 attB1	GACAAGTTTGTACAAAAAGCAGGCTCAATGGGTGAGGATATGCGAGTAGT	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT26 Kpn attB2	GACCACTTTGTACAAGAAAGCTGGGTACYATGCTTCCATATCTTTGTTCTTACC	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT27 attB1	GACAAGTTTGTACAAAAAGCAGGCTCAGAGGGAGAGATGGGTGAGGATAT	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT27 Kpn attB2	GACCACTTTGTACAAGAAAGCTGGGTACYAGACTCGTTGATCTTCGTTGTTTCAT	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT28 attB1	GACAAGTTTGTACAAAAAGCAGGCTCAAGAGATATGGCTGGAGATATGCA	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT28 Kpn attB2	GACCACTTTGTACAAGAAAGCTGGGTACYAAACGGGCGACTTAGAGTCGTTAT	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT28p attB1	GACAAGTTTGTACAAAAAGCAGGCTTCTCTCTTTTGAAGAGCCTT	Promoter cloning
AtUMAMIT28p attB2	GACCACTTTGTACAAGAAAGCTGGGTATCCTTGATATCTCCAGCCAT	Promoter cloning
AtUMAMIT29 attB1	GACAAGTTTGTACAAAAAGCAGGCTCAGAGAGAGAGAGAGGGATGATGAAG	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT29 Kpn attB2	GACCACTTTGTACAAGAAAGCTGGGTACYAAACGGGCAAATTAGTATCCTTATG	CDS cloning

AtUMAMIT29p attB1	GACAAGTTTGTACAAAAAAGCAGGCTCCGATTCTCCAAATTCAGGTA	Promoter cloning
AtUMAMIT29p attB2	GACCACTTTGTACAAGAAAGCTGGGTACCATTGTTCTTCCTTCATCAT	Promoter cloning
AtUMAMIT30 attB1	GACAAGTTTGTACAAAAAAGCAGGCTCACTAATCATGGGTTTTATCGATGGA	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT30 Kpn attB2	GACCACTTTGTACAAGAAAGCTGGGTACYAAGGAGTCATCGGAATAACCAAAAG	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT30p attB1	GACAAGTTTGTACAAAAAAGCAGGCTTTTGTGGTGGATGCAAGTAGTAGT	Promoter cloning
AtUMAMIT30p attB2	GACCACTTTGTACAAGAAAGCTGGGTACTTCCATCGATAAAACCCAT	Promoter cloning
AtUMAMIT31 attB1	GACAAGTTTGTACAAAAAAGCAGGCTCAATAATGGGTTACTGCGATGGTAAA	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT31 Kpn attB2	GACCACTTTGTACAAGAAAGCTGGGTACYAAGGAGTCATTGGAACAACCATAAG	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT32 attB1	GACAAGTTTGTACAAAAAAGCAGGCTCAATGGTAAAGTTTGATACAAAACATATGGA	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT32 Kpn attB2	GACCACTTTGTACAAGAAAGCTGGGTACYATTTTGCAGACACTTGATGGG	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT33 attB1	GACAAGTTTGTACAAAAAAGCAGGCTCAGAGATGGAGATATCGAAATACAAGG	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT33 Kpn attB2	GACCACTTTGTACAAGAAAGCTGGGTACYACATGAGAAGAGGTTCTAATAGCTCC	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT33p attB1	GACAAGTTTGTACAAAAAAGCAGGCTTGAGTTCGTTGAAGGTTTCGT	Promoter cloning
AtUMAMIT33p attB2	GACCACTTTGTACAAGAAAGCTGGGTATATCTCCATCTCTCTCTCTCTCT	Promoter cloning
AtUMAMIT34 attB1	GACAAGTTTGTACAAAAAAGCAGGCTCAATGGGGAAGATAGAGGAGTACAAG	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT34 Kpn attB2	GACCACTTTGTACAAGAAAGCTGGGTACYAGTATAGTTGTTGATGTGTTGGATTC	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT34p attB1	GACAAGTTTGTACAAAAAAGCAGGCTGACTCCCTCTCTGCACCAAGA	Promoter cloning
AtUMAMIT34p attB2	GACCACTTTGTACAAGAAAGCTGGGTAGTACTCCTCTATCTTCCCATGA	Promoter cloning
AtUMAMIT35 attB1	GACAAGTTTGTACAAAAAAGCAGGCTCAATGGGATTAATGGATACAAGATGG	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT35 Kpn attB2	GACCACTTTGTACAAGAAAGCTGGGTACYAAACTTGATCAAAATCACCATTCCG	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT36 attB1	GACAAGTTTGTACAAAAAAGCAGGCTCAATGGAGGTGAAGTTAGAAGAGAT	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT36 Kpn attB2	GACCACTTTGTACAAGAAAGCTGGGTACYATACAGGACTTTCTTCTGGTTAAT	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT37 attB1	GACAAGTTTGTACAAAAAAGCAGGCTCAATCAGATCTATGACAAGAGGAGCA	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT37 Kpn attB2	GACCACTTTGTACAAGAAAGCTGGGTACYAGTCACAGCTTAATGAGGCTTCTTC	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT38 attB1	GACAAGTTTGTACAAAAAAGCAGGCTCAATGAGAGAAGAGACAGTTTCTTGGA	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT38 Kpn attB2	GACCACTTTGTACAAGAAAGCTGGGTACYAACTTCTTCTCTGTCTGTGAAGG	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT40 attB1	GACAAGTTTGTACAAAAAAGCAGGCTCAATGAGAGAAGCAGGAGAAGAGAAA	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT40 Kpn attB2	GACCACTTTGTACAAGAAAGCTGGGTACYAGCTTAATGGAAAGGCTCCATCT	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT41 attB1	GACAAGTTTGTACAAAAAAGCAGGCTCAGAGAAAGAGAAGAAGATGGCGC	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT41 Kpn attB2	GACCACTTTGTACAAGAAAGCTGGGTACYATACATGTTTCATCGTTCTTGTAACTTTC	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT42 attB1	GACAAGTTTGTACAAAAAAGCAGGCTCAAAAATGGTTCATGGAAGGTTATGT	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT42 Kpn attB2	GACCACTTTGTACAAGAAAGCTGGGTACYAGCTTTTAAAATTATCCAAGAGAGGA	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT42p attB1	GACAAGTTTGTACAAAAAAGCAGGCTGAAGCTCTGCAAATCTGGCTTA	Promoter cloning
AtUMAMIT42p attB2	GACCACTTTGTACAAGAAAGCTGGGTAACATAACCTTCCATGAACCATT	Promoter cloning
AtUMAMIT44 attB1	GACAAGTTTGTACAAAAAAGCAGGCTCAACAATGGCCTCCATTACTCTCC	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT44 Kpn attB2	GACCACTTTGTACAAGAAAGCTGGGTACYATATTCGGTCTGCTATGTTTTCTGT	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT45 attB1	GACAAGTTTGTACAAAAAAGCAGGCTCATATCATTTCCTCAATAATGGCCC	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT45 Kpn attB2	GACCACTTTGTACAAGAAAGCTGGGTACYAGCCGTTCAATAGAAGAGGGGT	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT46 attB1	GACAAGTTTGTACAAAAAAGCAGGCTCACAAATTTTCTACCAATGCCAATA	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT46 Kpn attB2	GACCACTTTGTACAAGAAAGCTGGGTACYAAACTTGGTCTTTTTGCGGTTTAA	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT46p attB1	GACAAGTTTGTACAAAAAAGCAGGCTTAAACCATACTCAAAAAACTGTGG	Promoter cloning
AtUMAMIT46p attB2	GACCACTTTGTACAAGAAAGCTGGGTATCCGGCCATTATTGGCAT	Promoter cloning
AtUMAMIT47 attB1	GACAAGTTTGTACAAAAAAGCAGGCTCATTCTACCAATTTCCAATGGCC	CDS cloning

AtUMAMIT47 Kpn attB2	GACCACTTTGTACAAGAAAGCTGGGTACyAAATTTGGTCGTTTTTGCCG	CDS cloning
AtUMAMIT14-01 SOE f	CACTCTGCAATGACATTGGTTC	N-terminus exchange
AtUMAMIT14-01 SOE r	ACCAATGTCATTGCAGAGTGTGGCTTCCATGTTTTTAAAGC	N-terminus exchange
AtUMAMIT14-08 SOE f	ATCGGAGGATTGGCCG	N-terminus exchange
AtUMAMIT14-08 SOE r	GCTCCGGCCAATCCTCCGATTGGCTTCCATGTTTTTAAAGC	N-terminus exchange
AtUMAMIT14-33 SOE f	GTGCTAGCGTTAGTGATGTTGC	N-terminus exchange
AtUMAMIT14-33 SOE r	AACATCACTAACGCTAGCACTGGCTTCCATGTTTTTAAAGC	N-terminus exchange
AtUMAMIT14-34 SOE f	GTAATGGCGATGACGATGATT	N-terminus exchange
AtUMAMIT14-34 SOE r	ATCATCGTCATCGCCATTACTGGCTTCCATGTTTTTAAAGC	N-terminus exchange
AtUMAMIT14-40 SOE f	TTTGCTGCGATGTTTGCG	N-terminus exchange
AtUMAMIT14-40 SOE r	ACCGCAAACATCGCAGCAAATGGCTTCCATGTTTTTAAAGC	N-terminus exchange
AtUMAMIT14-44 SOE f	TTGACGGCCATGTTGGC	N-terminus exchange
AtUMAMIT14-44 SOE r	GTCGCCAACATGGCCGTCAATGGCTTCCATGTTTTTAAAGC	N-terminus exchange

Supplementary Fig. S1. Multiple sequence alignment of 180 UMAMIT sequences. Proteins from Arabidopsis, rice, pine, *Selaginella* and *Physcomitrella* were aligned using ClustalW. Residues mutated in UMAMIT4 are localized on the alignment at positions 96 (G33), 204 (E122), 212 (K134), 227 (G144) and 435 (G315). Letters A to J on the left correspond to the clades from Figure 1.

Supplementary Fig. S2. Distribution of the mRNA contents of the *AtUMAMIT* genes in Arabidopsis in various conditions and organs. Violin plot of the mRNA content determined by RNAseq from 1229 publicly available samples, extracted from Genevestigator-normalized data in August 2020 (details about normalization can be obtained from Genevestigator support). Plots are colored based on the average expression of the genes.

Supplementary Fig. S3. Position of the *AtUMAMIT* genes on the Arabidopsis chromosomes. The position of the genes was determined using the Chromosome Map Tool from TAIR (<https://www.arabidopsis.org/>). Color schemes correspond to the clades from Fig. 1, and the curved lines highlight the closely related genes.

Bootstrap (%)
100 85 70
Scale (amino acid substitution per site)
0.2

Abbreviation	Group	Name
FaHem	Fabid	<i>Nemolol esculenta</i>
FaRic	Fabid	<i>Ricinus communis</i>
FaLin	Fabid	<i>Linum usitatissimum</i>
FaPop	Fabid	<i>Populus trichocarpa</i>
FaMed	Fabid	<i>Medicago truncatula</i>
FaPha	Fabid	<i>Phaseolus vulgaris</i>
FaGly	Fabid	<i>Glycine max</i>
FaCuc	Fabid	<i>Cucumis sativus</i>
FaPru	Fabid	<i>Prunus persica</i>
FaMal	Fabid	<i>Malus domestica</i>
FaFra	Fabid	<i>Fragaria vesca</i>
AtUmam	Malvid	<i>Arabidopsis thaliana</i>
MaCap	Malvid	<i>Capsella rubella</i>
MaBra	Malvid	<i>Brassica rapa</i>
MaThi	Malvid	<i>Thellungiella halophylla</i>
MaCar	Malvid	<i>Carica papaya</i>
MaGos	Malvid	<i>Gossypium raimondii</i>
MaThe	Malvid	<i>Theobroma cacao</i>
MaCit	Malvid	<i>Citrus sinensis</i>
MaCit	Malvid	<i>Citrus clementina</i>
MaEuc	Malvid	<i>Eucalyptus grandis</i>
RvVit	Rosid	<i>Vitis vinifera</i>
AsSol	Asterid	<i>Solanum lycopersicum</i>
AsMim	Asterid	<i>Mimulus guttatus</i>
RuAgu	Ranunculales	<i>Aquilegia coerulea</i>
MoSor	Monocots	<i>Sorghum bicolor</i>
MoZea	Monocots	<i>Zea mays</i>
MoSet	Monocots	<i>Setaria italica</i>
MoPan	Monocots	<i>Panicum virgatum</i>
OxUmam	Monocots	<i>Oryza sativa</i>
MoBra	Monocots	<i>Brachypodium distachyon</i>
CoPic	Conifers	<i>Picea abies</i>
CoPin	Conifers	<i>Pinus pinaster</i>
TrSel	Tracheophyta	<i>VSelaginella moellendorffii</i>
BrPh	Bryophyta	<i>Physcomitrella patens</i>
MaMic	Mamiellales	<i>Micromonas pusilla</i>
MaMic	Mamiellales	<i>Micromonas pusilla</i>
MaOst	Mamiellales	<i>Osteococcus lucimarinus</i>
TrCoc	Trebouxiphyceae	<i>Coccomyxa subellipsoida</i>

Supplementary Fig. S4. Phylogenetic tree of 1466 UMAMIT proteins. Proteins names are colored by species, see left panel; # indicate rice sequences; * indicates Arabidopsis sequences. Colored dots on the branches indicate bootstrap values of 1000 replicates. The tree was constructed using RaxML from sequences of Supplementary Dataset S1. Letters and numbers around the radial tree indicate Clades and Subclades.

Supplementary Fig. S6. Model of the predicted AtUMAMIT14 protein dimer. The model was created by Swissmodel. Colors correspond to the homologous helices in the protein (e.g. A1 and B1 are in orange) to show the arrangement of the transmembrane domains of the two structural repeats. Loops are colored in gray, except the extra-cytoplasmic loop located between structural repeats A and B colored in yellow. Red: mutagenized residues.

Plant organs

Root development

Seed development

Supplementary Fig. S7. PCA analysis of the localization of the expression of the *AtUMAMIT* genes in the plant. Data from Supplementary Dataset S3A, B and C were processed using JMP. The color of the circles around the best individualized genes corresponds to the Clades from Fig. 1.

AtUMAMIT02

AtUMAMIT03

AtUMAMIT04

AtUMAMIT11

AtUMAMIT12

AtUMAMIT22

AtUMAMIT23

AtUMAMIT24

AtUMAMIT28

AtUMAMIT29

AtUMAMIT30

AtUMAMIT33

AtUMAMIT34

AtUMAMIT42

AtUMAMIT46

Supplementary Fig. S8. Expression patterns of 15 *AtUMAMIT* promoters. Plants expressing AtUMAMITp-GUS plants were grown on soil for 5-6 weeks, and the organs were stained independently. (A) Inflorescence / flower. (B) Stem or stem cross-section. (C) Leaf detail. (D) Stamen. (E) Leaf epidermis.

Supplementary Fig. S9. Localization in the plant of 13 *AtUMAMIT* genes obtained from translato-me data. Data were obtained from <http://efp.ucr.edu/cgi-bin/absolute.cgi>. mRNA localization was obtained by translato-me analysis of transgenic plants that express a tagged ribosomal protein in specific cell types (Mustroph et al., 2009). This approach does not use making protoplasts from cells, contrary to the root expression dataset used in Supplementary Dataset S3B. Data for *AtUMAMIT23* and *24* could not be retrieved from the server.

Mustroph A, Zanetti ME, Jang CJ, Holtan HE, Repetti PP, Galbraith DW, Girke T, Bailey-Serres J. 2009. Profiling translato-mes of discrete cell populations resolves altered cellular priorities during hypoxia in Arabidopsis. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Science Of USA* **106**, 18843-18848.

Supplementary Fig. S10. PCA analysis of the change in expression of the *AtUMAMIT* genes in the plant. Data from Supplementary Dataset S3D, E, F and G were processed using JMP. The color of the circles around the best individualized genes corresponds to the Clades from Fig. 1.

Supplementary Fig. S11. Correlation between change in mRNA expression and expression level of the *AtUMAMITs*. The averages of the mRNA levels from RNAseq data retrieved from Genevestigator (same data as Supplementary Fig. 2) were plotted against the variances of the fold change from the AtGenExpress dataset (hormones, stress, pathogens and root treatment, from Supplementary Dataset S3). Each data point represent one *AtUMAMIT* gene.

AtUMAIMT22

AtUMAIMT23

AtUMAIMT24

AtUMAIMT28

AtUMAIM29

AtUMAIMT30

AtUMAIMT33

AtUMAIMT34

AtUMAIMT42

AtUMAIMT46

Supplementary Fig. S12. Localization of GUS activity of plants expressing GUS under the control of *AtUMAMIT* promoters. Plants were grown in vitro on media containing low nitrogen (LN) or high nitrogen (1/2 MS medium - MS). For each gene, the staining reaction of plants grown on the LN or MS media was let proceed for the same amount of time, but the reaction time can be different from one gene to another.

Cross-section

Supplementary Fig. S13. Subcellular localization of the AtUMAMITs proteins expressed in *N. benthamiana* cells. AtUMAMITs were expressed with the GFP fused at their C-terminus in *Nicotiana benthamiana* leaf epidermis, and observed by confocal microscopy. A z-stack of at least 12 sections was constructed; cross-section images were taken from the z-stack. Scale bar = 5 μ M.

A

ATUMAMIT01-----MAAPA**IL**NG-GDA**TE**R**E**TRMAHSA
ATUMAMIT02-----MTAP**MI**L**T**GS**GS**AA**ER**DARMAHTA
ATUMAMIT03-----ME**ST**V**ER**EAWKAHVA
ATUMAMIT04-----MGKGV--V**SE**K**V**K**L**VVA
ATUMAMIT05-----MAD**NT**D**N**RR**SL**WG**VP**E**K**L**QL**HIA
ATUMAMIT06-----M**SP**I**PE**RA**L**HIA
ATUMAMIT07-MQFFCVN**LY**RS**VL**N**LL**E**ER**M**K**T**EM**I**E**M**V**I**V**GG
ATUMAMIT08-----MMK**RE**T**L**I**E**AG**I**I**GG**
ATUMAMIT09-----MS**ME**I**SS**C**ES**F**L**T**SS**K**P**Y**FA**
ATUMAMIT10-----M**GL**K**MS**E**S**AK**P**Y**FA**
ATUMAMIT11-----M**GL**R**MS**E**S**AK**P**Y**FA**
ATUMAMIT12-----M**EE**V**K**K**R**D**CM**E**K**AR**P**F**IS**
ATUMAMIT13-----MAC**M**K**K**A**L**P**F**I**L**
ATUMAMIT14-----M**AL**K**T**W**K**P**F**I**T**
ATUMAMIT15-----M**K**F**ER**AR**P**F**IA**
ATUMAMIT17-----M**K**G**G**K**M**D**K**L**K**P**II**A
ATUMAMIT18-----M**K**G**G**S**ME**K**I**K**P**I**LA**
ATUMAMIT19-----M**GR**G**L**M**NS**L**K**P**Y**L**A**
ATUMAMIT20-----M**E**G**V**SAT**M**H**K**L**R**P**Y**L**L**
ATUMAMIT21-----M**DM**E**S**K**K**P**Y**L**M**
ATUMAMIT22-----M**MM**E**H**KAN**M**A**M**
ATUMAMIT23-----M**K**D**I**T**A**
ATUMAMIT24-----M**K**S**V**V**A**
ATUMAMIT25-----MA**K**S**D**M**L**P**F**L**A**
ATUMAMIT26-----M**G**E**D**M**R**V**V**K**V**E**S**K**W**P**P**I**I**V
ATUMAMIT27-----M**G**E**D**M**R**G**V**K**V**V**S**K**W**P**P**M**I**V
ATUMAMIT28-----M**A**G**D**M**Q**G**V**R**V**V**E**K**Y**S**P**V**I**V
ATUMAMIT29-----M**M**K**EE**Q**W**A**P**V**I**V
ATUMAMIT30-----M**G**F**I**D**G**K**W**A**P**M**I**V
ATUMAMIT31-----M**G**Y**CD**G**K**W**T**P**V**I**I**
ATUMAMIT32-----M**V**K**F**D**T**K**L**W**K**A**V**L**M**
ATUMAMIT33-----M**E**I**S**K**Y**K**A**V**L**A
ATUMAMIT34-----M**G**K**I**E**E**Y**K**P**V**M**A**
ATUMAMIT35-----M**G**L**MD**T**R**W**E**T**I**V**P**F**I**V
ATUMAMIT36-----M**E**V**K**V**RR**D**E**L**V**P**F**V**A**
ATUMAMIT37-----M**T**R**G**A**GG**E**T**V**A**W**S**Y**F**C**R**D**V**V**P**F**T**A
ATUMAMIT38-----M**R**---**E**E**T**V**S**W**K**Y**F**K**R**D**V**V**P**F**T**A
ATUMAMIT40-----M**R**E**A**G**EE**K**V**A**W**K**Y**F**T**R**D**V**V**P**F**AA
ATUMAMIT41-----M**A**R**K**Y**F**Q**R**E**V**L**P**V**T**A
ATUMAMIT42-----M**V**H**G**R**L**C**N**R**D**G**W**I**L**T**A**
ATUMAMIT44-----M**A**-**S**I**T**L**RRR**D**A**V**L**L**T**A
ATUMAMIT45-----M**A**R**T**V**S**L**W**R**R**E**A**V**F**L**T**A
ATUMAMIT46-----M**P**I**M**A**G**T**A**S**P**W**R**R**E**A**V**F**L**T**A**
ATUMAMIT47-----M**A**G**A**V**S**L**W**R**R**E**A**V**F**L**T**A

B

ATUMAMIT01 WAS**Y**RE**Q**QTTSAGNE**I**ASSSD**V**R**I**SE**P**FI**R**DE**T**GK
ATUMAMIT02 WASFR**E**RKTAVSG**I**GIAPHGLK**T**SE**P**LI**F**NGTVN**R**L**G**Q**L**F**S**GL**P**SS**S**V**K**S**A**D
ATUMAMIT03 WAS**Y**K**E**KKAAAAMAV**I**P**T**TSK**E**A**E**PL**I**Y**K**D**H**KN**K**P**I**GH**L**F**T**K**S**P**I**SS**P**K**S**D**D**
ATUMAMIT04 WGKN**E**ER**K**L**A**LE**E**S**Q**Q**D**PE**S**L**T**K**H**LL**E**A**Q**H**K**K**S**NS**E**SE**V**
ATUMAMIT05 **Y**GKS**E**ER**K**FA**A**LE**K**AA**I**QSS**A**E**H**GI**E**RA**P**V**S**R**N**S**I**K**S**S**I**TT**P**LL**H**Q**S**T**D**N**V**
ATUMAMIT06 MGK**S**W**E**N**Q**AL**C**QQ**Q**QH**M**ISS**A**AS**D**FG**D**E**E**D**Y**H**N**N**K**PR**S**P**I**S**Q**PL**I**SS
ATUMAMIT07 WAKG**K**EG**F**SE**I**ES**F**ES**E**F**D**SK**K**PL**L**S
ATUMAMIT08 WAKG**K**ED**C**EE**I**DE**M**K**Q**DE**E**S**L**LR**T**E**F**DL**Q**K**P**LL**L**
ATUMAMIT09 WGK**Q**KE**N**Q**V**T**I**CE**L**AK**I**D**S**NS**K**V**T**ED**V**EANGSK**M**K**I**SE**G**DN**S**ML**S**T**I**V**I**SV**P**LS**E**TH**L**KK**T**I**Q**E**P**
ATUMAMIT10 WGK**E**GD**I**DE**E**EN**I**EE**K**F**V**E**I**V**K**CC**N**RC**D**I**K**VL**S**MM**P**R**I**DE**E**V**D**VE**M**Q**S**AG**T**AK**V**AV**G**FS
ATUMAMIT11 WGKH**V**DD**D**GE**E**TR**H**ED**N**V**V**AV**K**CC**S**GN**N**GL**T**IMP**K**I**D**E**A**DE**E**D**V**ET**G**K**A**T**S**E**K**E**S**SV**P**E**V**VVV**V**FC**S**E**N**V**H**SV**S**R**I**
ATUMAMIT12 WGK**G**K**D**Y**K**Y**N**ST**L**Q**L**DE**S**A**Q**P**K**LE**L**SG**N**G**K**D**N**V**D**HE**V**IT**I**SK**Q**GE**Q**RR**T**AV**E**T**V**
ATUMAMIT13 WGK**A**K**D**Y**E**Y**P**ST**P**Q**I**DD**D**LA**Q**AT**T**SK**Q**KE**Q**RR**T**V**I**ES**V**
ATUMAMIT14 WGK**S**K**D**EP**S**SS**F**S**D**MD**K**EL**L**PL**S**T**P**Q**I**V**L**PS**K**AN**A**K**M**D**T**ND**A**SV**V**I**S**R**P**NT**N**ES**V**
ATUMAMIT15 WGK**S**K**D**KG**G**ML**Q**P**N**AG**C**A**E**T**V**V**K**I**D**Q**Q**K**V**PT**P**DN**N**Q**V**V**S**I**S**Y**H**LM**I**PK**A**A**A**RS**Q**E
ATUMAMIT17 WGK**A**K**D**E**V**IS**V**EE**K**I**G**M**Q**EL**P**IT**N**T**S**T**K**VE**G**GG**I**T**S**EV**N**E**G**V**T**N**N**T**Q**V
ATUMAMIT18 WGK**S**K**D**E**V**NP**L**DE**K**I**V**AK**S**Q**EL**P**I**T**N**V**V**K**Q**T**N**GH**D**V**S**G**A**P**T**NG**V**V**T**ST
ATUMAMIT19 WGK**G**K**D**K**R**MT**DD**DE**D**CK**G**LP**I**K**S**P**V**K**P**V**D**T**G**K**L**A**E**LE**M**K**S**KE**G**Q**E**AK**A**T**T**T**T**Q**V**E**I**
ATUMAMIT20 WGK**G**K**D**Y**E**VS**G**LD**I**LE**K**NS**L**Q**EL**P**I**TT**K**S**E**DD**N**KL**V**SS**I**SD**N**SN**V**T**I**PG**G**A**H**S**N**T**S**GI
ATUMAMIT21 WGK**S**R**E**E**K**NS**G**DD**K**I**D**L**Q**KE**N**D**V**VC**N**E**V**K**V**IS
ATUMAMIT22 WGK**T**K**E**E**E**I**Q**RY**G**E**K**Q**S**Q**K**E**I**I**E**E**V**I**V**
ATUMAMIT23 WAK**N**K**E**M**K**S**M**L**T**TS**D**H**N**E**T**N**K**T**S**K**D**I**T**V**N**N**L**P**T**L**S**T**N**V**P**
ATUMAMIT24 WCK**M**K**E**KS**A**ST**T**S**D**H**I**E**T**N**K**N**K**EL**D**L**G**N**L**SS**V**N**R**D**V**P
ATUMAMIT25 WGK**D**RE**V**SE**K**EE**E**RE**K**V**K**Q**N**H**K**V**K**SE**S**NE**D**IE**S**R**L**P**V**ASS**G**NG**S**TR**S**T**S**P
ATUMAMIT26 WGK**N**K**D**ME**A**
ATUMAMIT27 WGK**N**K**E**TE**A**D**I**TT**L**SS**R**M**N**NE**D**Q**R**V
ATUMAMIT28 WGK**N**K**E**TES**S**T**A**L**S**SG**M**D**N**E**A**Q**Y**TT**P**N**K**D**N**D**S**K**S**P**V**
ATUMAMIT29 WGR**K**N**E**T**D**Q**S**V**S**K**T**LN**S**S**Q**F**S**Q**N**K**D**NE**D**HT**I**AN**H**K**D**T**N**L**P**V
ATUMAMIT30 WSR**S**K**Q**I**V**E**C**K**I**M**K**L**P**T**N**T**V**EE**E**K**E**E**E**GR**T**N**V**N**G**Q**L**L**V**I**P**M**T**P
ATUMAMIT31 LG**K**V**R**L**M**K**E**E**C**E**K**L**P**CR**F**N**E**DD**Q**E**ED**D**D**E**Q**Y**K**G**H**L**M**V**V**P**M**T**P**
ATUMAMIT32 WGK**S**K**D**KS**A**SV**T**K**Q**E**P**L**D**L**D**I**E**GC**G**T**A**PK**E**LN**S**T**A**H**Q**V**S**A**K**
ATUMAMIT33 WGKS**E**D**Y**Q**E**EST**D**L**K**LE**N**E**H**NT**S**S**Q**S**D**I**V**S**I**M**I**G**D**K**A**FR**S**SE**L**LE**P**LL**M**
ATUMAMIT34 WGK**A**K**D**V**M**M**N**Q**D**Q**R**D**N**D**Q**KS**E**V**K**I**H**I**E**D**S**S**N**T**T**I**C**N**K**D**L**K**N**P**L**L**S**K**H**K**S**T**E**E**I**Q**T**H**Q**Q**L**Y
ATUMAMIT35 WS**Q**V**Q**K**DD**PN**E**T**V**E**K**N**D**N**H**Q**L**D**S**DE**Q**T**P**LLL**A**NG**D**F**D**Q**V**
ATUMAMIT36 WG**Q**L**K**ES**E**E**K**Q**S**SN**E**ER**K**S**I**K**T**I**H**H**R**DE**D**E**Y**K**V**P**L**L**I**N**Q**EE**S**P**V**
ATUMAMIT37 WGK**A**R**E**D**S**I**K**T**V**AG**T**E**Q**SP**L**L**P**SH**T**IE**E**E**A**SL**S**C**D**
ATUMAMIT38 WGK**A**R**E**D**S**T**K**T**V**SD**E**Q**S**LLL**P**SH**D**RE**E**D
ATUMAMIT40 WGK**A**R**E**D**T**I**K**T**V**AG**S**E**Q**SP**L**L**L**TH**I**I**E**D**G**A**F**PL**S**
ATUMAMIT41 WGK**A**K**E**VAL**V**ED**D**N**K**AN**H**EE**A**NE**A**D**L**D**S**PS**G**S**Q**K**A**PL**L**ES**Y**K**N**DE**H**V
ATUMAMIT42 WGK**A**K**E**D**K**V**D**I**I**G**A**IE**S**SP**S**H**N**A**P**LL**D**N**F**K**S**
ATUMAMIT44 WGK**A**K**E**G**K**T**Q**FL**S**LS**E**ET**P**LL**D**EN**I**DD**R**I
ATUMAMIT45 WGK**A**N**E**E**K**D**Q**LLL**V**SG**K**ERT**P**LLL**N**G
ATUMAMIT46 WGK**A**N**E**E**K**D**Q**LS**F**SE**K**E**K**TP**L**LL**N**R**K**N**D**Q**V**
ATUMAMIT47 WGK**A**N**E**E**K**N**K**LL**S**F**S**G**K**E**K**TP**L**LL**S**G**K**N**D**Q**I**

Supplementary Fig. S14. Alignment of the N- and C- termini of the AtUMAMITs. (A) Alignment of the sequences from the beginning of the protein to the transmembrane domain A1 (N-terminus). (B) Alignment of the sequences from the end of the transmembrane domain B5 to the end of the protein (C-terminus). Acidic residues are in red, aromatic residues in green, and Leu and Ile in blue. Proteins detected at the tonoplast are in bold, while proteins detected at the plasma membrane are underlined (see Table 1).

Supplementary Fig. S15. Subcellular localization of the AtUMAMIT proteins without and with N-terminus exchange. Each protein was expressed in *N. benthamiana* epidermis cells with the YFP fused to their C-terminus. For each studied protein, the unmodified protein localization is presented on top, and the modified protein (for which the N-terminus of AtUMAMIT14 replaced the native N-terminus) at the bottom of each panel. The section and transmission images were taken from a series of a z-stack, for which a projection was created to show the pattern of the fluorescence in the cell (z-stack). Red arrows point to chloroplasts to emphasize the tonoplast or plasma membrane localization.

Supplementary Fig. S16. PCA analysis of amino acid export profiles of the AtUMAMITs expressed in yeast. Data from Supplementary Dataset S4 were processed in JMP. (A) PCA plot, with the most individualized proteins labeled. (B) Loading plot with names of the corresponding amino acids. This graph shows three groups of amino acids whose content correlates with one-another inside each group: (1) Glu, Asp and GABA, (2) Gln, Val and Ile, (3) Pro, Ser, Phe, Ala, Thr, Leu and Met.

Supplementary Fig. S17. Methionine uptake complementation assay of yeast expressing the AtUMAMITs. 22Δ10α cells transformed with plasmids leading to the expression of the AtUMAMITs, or AAP3 (+) or with the empty vector (-) were streaked on plasmid-selective SD medium and grown at 29°C for 3 days, resuspended in H₂O, diluted to OD₆₀₀ = 0.6, 0.06, 0.006, and 0.0006, and spotted on assay medium with 3 mM Met as the sole nitrogen source.

Scale bar: 20 μ M

Supplementary Fig. S18. Expression and localization of the wild type and variants of AtUMAMIT14-GFP expressed in yeast cells. Strain 23344c (parental of 22 Δ 10 α) was transformed with constructs leading to the expression of wild type and AtUMAMIT14 variants fused to the GFP. Cells were grown on solid SD medium for two days and imaged by light microscopy. All pictures were taken with exactly the same settings (amount of light and exposure) to emphasize differences in fluorescence intensities.